

Study of an underground cistern as a thermal storage with HVACR system via heat pump assisted by PV: the case of the IWER building in Pamplona

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0.ABSTRACT

Given the global uncertainty surrounding energy prices and the urgent need to improve energy efficiency in the building sector, sustainable rehabilitation is becoming increasingly important. This is particularly true in the case of Spain, where the building sector is largely outdated. In response to this challenge, the OpenLab European project aims to refurbish the IWER building, a tertiary building located in Pamplona. The proposed HVACR system will be based on heat pumps supported by a large photovoltaic installation and contemplates a singular feature: an existing underground water cistern that can be used as a thermal storage. The use of such storage system can help compensate the inherent lack of flexibility in the energy consumption patterns of buildings in the tertiary sector.

The study involves a real-case simulation of a sustainable rehabilitation project, which expands previous general-case studies of solar assisted heat pumps with thermal storage for smaller, primarily residential buildings. To achieve that objective, simulations are performed by the Design Builder software using hourly data analysis. Different sizing and control strategies will be applied to meet the specific needs of the involved tertiary building. The results of the study show three main benefits: a reduction of the total HVACR installed power by using the thermal storage for peak shaving; an improved control of the HVACR production by decoupling production and demand while stabilizing the regime of the heat pumps, and, finally, a maximized photovoltaic self-consumption coupled with a shift of the electricity load to cheaper and more sustainable electricity consumption hours.

1. INTRODUCTION

Global warming is one of the most important scientific, engineering and social issues of this century. One of the many ways to fight against is energy efficiency, the reduction of energy expenditure through a better and optimized use of energy [1]. In this context, buildings are consumers of 40% of energy in Europe and 36% of greenhouse gas emissions [2], within which buildings destined to the tertiary sector in Spain are responsible for about 40% of building consumption [3]. In response, the use of renewable energy as well as more efficient technologies such as heat pumps have been widely applied in both the tertiary and residential sectors and have promoted their electrification [4]. This increased electrification has led to a rise in energy storage technologies: batteries, thermal storage, etc., due to two different factors: an uncertainty about the price and environmental impact of the electricity consumed and a highly variable demand curve, driven by the dependence of HVACR systems on climatic conditions [5]. The residential sector has been analyzed in greater depth, for example by Li et al and Rinaldi et al [6,7], but research in the tertiary sector in relation to thermal storage is in a nascent state, with studies such as the one conducted by Ragoowansi et al [8] recently.

In this context, the oPEN Lab project was born, whose main objective is the improvement of existing buildings and districts in three neighborhoods in the European cities of Tartu, Pamplona and Genk. In this project, the rehabilitation of the IWER complex in Pamplona will be addressed. It includes among its original facilities a 560m³ useful volume cistern, whose use as a thermal storage system will be analyzed in this work. This will be linked to the premise that the HVACR installation of the building will be carried out using heat pumps and photovoltaic energy on the roof.

To understand the benefits of using a storage tank in a heat pump system, some details are explained below. If the heat pumps operate without a storage tank, the thermal load of the building has to be covered in real time, so the pumps must be sized to cover the peak load, even though in a large percentage of hours of the year they do not operate at full load but at partial load [9]. This phenomenon can be alleviated with a storage tank. The heat pump feeds the tank and the tank feeds the demand, so that the heat pump can be sized at a lower load and use the tank to supply peak shaving. Secondly, heat pumps can always operate at nominal load with a more stable on/off regime. There are studies in the literature on this phenomenon [6,10], where a reduction in the installed power of heat pumps was achieved through the use of thermal storage and also a regularization of their operation that resulted in operational benefits.

Another possible benefit of thermal storage is the shifting of the working hours of the heat pumps to those that are preferable, by means of control strategies. This is especially important in systems with photovoltaic production, as they often have surplus energy that cannot be stored otherwise and must be consumed as it is generated. This exploitation has been studied by Dannemand et al., Heinz & Rieberer and Sohani et al. [11-13], where lower grid power consumption was achieved in simulations performed for buildings in the residential sector. Among the various control strategies for this higher PV energy harvesting, the present work will be based on those followed by Heinz & Rieberer [11]. In that study they found that by shifting heat pump production to sunny hours and changing the storage temperature setpoints to "overcharge" during hours of excess PV, up to 4% grid energy savings could be achieved. A different control strategy tested particularly in the residential sector through the use of batteries and also thermal storage is to adapt electricity consumption to the price of grid electricity, so as to encourage consumption in low price hours and avoid high price hours. This has been studied among others by Agyenim & Hewitt, Palani et al. and Pardo et al. [14-16].

These thermal storage techniques and control strategies have been studied mainly in the residential sector, as presented in the review of heat pump and thermal storage systems for buildings by Osterman & Stritih [17]. In it, more than 40 studies on TES with heat pumps are analyzed, although only one of them has an installed power and storage tank size similar to the magnitudes of this study (560m³ and demand of the order of 1500kW). This mentioned study was conducted by Kim et al [18] for an office building in South Korea. However, no control strategies were studied as a function of PV or off-peak hours.

Thus, this paper aims to evaluate the benefits of thermal storage in the real case of the IWER complex. The main objective is to analyze whether the benefits found in the state of the art on the use of thermal storage in the residential sector would apply to the case study of the IWER complex using its subway cistern as storage tank. These potential benefits are:

- Reduction of installed power in pumps thanks to peak shaving through the energy stored in the tank.

- Stabilization of the pump(s) regime, less starts and stops, more time at nominal load by partially decoupling demand from consumption.

- Energy and/or economic savings through the use of control strategies based on excess photovoltaic energy and electricity prices.

2. METHODOLOGY

Briefly introducing the IWER building, an aerial image of the building can be seen in Figure 1. This building is an old textile factory in the Rochapea neighborhood of Pamplona. The historical value and the good structural condition of the building has led to the consideration not of its demolition, but of its energetic rehabilitation with the aim of reviving the social climate of the neighborhood. Three of the four industrial buildings annexed to the building will be demolished to make room for a tree-lined square and the rest of the building will be maintained for different uses. The main use is offices on the middle and upper floors, but it will also have a gym, a supermarket, a nursing home, a loft complex and businesses open to the public on the first floor. This is the first interesting element for the thermal analysis of this building, its uses are diverse and so is the thermal demand curve, therefore requiring powerful thermal calculation tools for its analysis. The second reason for choosing this building for a thermal storage study is the presence of a subway cistern with a useful volume of 560m³. This cistern, marked in yellow in figure 1, being already present in the building does not require excavation and installation works, and only few studies have been carried out with water tanks already installed to evaluate a TES. This already existing subway cistern together with the variety of uses for the demand of the building gives rise to the interest of this particular case study, where techniques of using a TES usually studied in buildings of the residential sector will be evaluated and adapted to a high demand multipurpose building, mainly tertiary.

Fig.1: Aerial view of IWER complex and it's cistern.

First, a 3D CAD model of the IWER complex was imported from REVIT into Design Builder. After this partly automated import process with manual adjustments, the result is a geometric model of the IWER complex divided into zones according to their use, in total more than 50 zones. Secondly, a generic thermal envelope model was applied.

This study does not delve into the thermal envelope and therefore an existing envelope template in Design Builder called "Medium weight, moderate insulation" was used. Thirdly, an activity model was applied to each zone that reproduces a behavior faithful to the uses of each zone. For this purpose, both the basic DBHE document and the CTE were followed so that variables such as occupancy profiles, thermal power of equipment, lighting, etc., could be used. The rendered model of the IWER complex can be seen in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Rendered model of the IWER complex in Design Builder

Finally, the HVACR systems without and with thermal storage were designed using the advanced HVAC module of Design Builder. The setpoint temperatures for cooling are 7°C-12°C and for heating 45°C-40°C, i.e. a thermal jump of 5°C of the working fluid. To meet this need, water-to-water heat pumps were used, leaving Design Builder the job of auto-dimensioning as many variables as possible. Heat storage occurs between 50°C and 45°C, with overload up to 60°C and cold storage occurs between 5°C and 9°C, with overload up to 2°C. No heat losses have been modeled as this was a preliminary proof-of-concept study. The result of the HVACR system design in Design Builder following these assumptions is shown in Figure 3. In this model the heat pumps used are a model already introduced in Design Builder of a water-to-water heat pump with its operating curve introduced, and the number of heat pumps that satisfy the rated power adequately with the model used are between 4 and 5 heat pumps in parallel.

Fig. 3: HVACR system scheme

For the analysis, 3 weeks have been studied in each of the characteristic periods of the year. These periods are:

- Winter week (January 15 to 22). This period will determine the sizing of heating and will be used to analyze control strategies with low photovoltaic production, based on electricity prices.
- Summer week (July 8 to 15). This period will determine the sizing of cooling and will be used to analyze control strategies with high PV production, based on the use of excess production.
- Intermediate week (autumn): (October 7 to 14). This period will be used to determine the effect of simultaneous heating and cooling as well as to analyze mixed control strategies based on excess photovoltaic production and control based on electricity prices, all this in a period where the thermal load is not maximum.

The block diagram of the algorithm used to obtain the described models is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Block diagram of reduced power obtention algorithm

•Photovoltaic exploitation: On days when there is excess photovoltaic during the hours of excess all heat pumps are turned on to charge the TES up to its overload setpoint, and outside these hours only 1 heat pump can operate if and only if the TES reaches its discharge temperature.

•Electricity price-based control: Electricity free market prices in Spain were used to determine the highest and lowest price hours. These coincide with the “valley”, “flat” and “peak” hours of the Spanish PVPC price approximately. During the lowest price hours (valley) the tank is overcharged, during the intermediate hours (flat) the tank is charged but not overcharged and during the most expensive hours (peak) the heat pumps are deactivated except for one in case a slight compensation is necessary in order not to lower the temperature below the set point temperature.

3. RESULTS

The first result is the reduction of installed power. The HVACR system with heat pumps without storage was sized to the minimum possible power, and then in the model with storage the power was further reduced until just before the thermal comfort conditions were no longer met. The resulting electrical power requirement for the heat pumps was:

- In winter: 960kW without storage and 788kW with storage; 18% reduction.
- In summer: 859kW without storage and 726kW with storage; 15% reduction.

The second result is the regularization of heat pump operation. Both in winter and in summer, the heat pump needed for consumption peaks, which used to operate many times off and at partial powers, manages to operate in a much more stable nominal power regime, reducing start-ups, shutdowns and their negative consequences.

This result can be clearly observed in figure 5, where the simulation in winter is shown. On the left can be seen the operation of the heat pumps during the winter week without TES, where up to 4 heat pumps are necessary to cover the demand in the peaks that occur early in the working morning. On the right-hand side you can see the model with thermal storage, where with just 3 heat pumps the demand was met. Looking at the curve on the left the first two heat pumps work 24 hours a day (red and blue curves overlap), but the 3rd and 4th only during peaks. The thermal storage causes the 3rd heat pump to operate more hours at rated power and these extra hours are used in peak shaving, reducing the maximum installed heat pump power necessity.

Fig. 5: Thermal power of heat pumps in winter week. On the left without storage and on the right with storage.

The third result is an improvement in energy efficiency through the use of control strategies. For different installed powers, the behavior of the system was simulated without storage, with storage and with storage and control strategies. This section summarizes the results of the simulations with 4 of the heat pumps used, representing the minimum power without storage.

Figure 6 presents the results, where the values of the simulations without thermal storage have been taken as 100%. The year of study is 2022, but the winter strategy by price-dependent control was also studied in 2023, marked by the superscript in the table.

The results show several phenomena:

- The thermal jump of the heat pumps increases due to the storage temperatures being higher in heating and lower in cooling in order to accumulate (Ex: The chilled water demand for cooling is at 7°C but it accumulates even up to 2°C). This causes a reduction of the COP of the heat pumps and an increase of their electrical consumption. This increase in consumption is a negative phenomenon that will affect the possible savings through control strategies.

- The savings strategy based on photovoltaic utilization has the best results. It shows positive results both in summer and autumn, causing a 7% reduction in grid energy consumption compared to the model without TES and control strategies.

- The control strategy as a function of the hourly price has positive effects, as it at least partly compensates the extra consumption caused by the higher thermal jump even in winter and leads to higher savings in autumn. The variation is large depending on the electricity price.

Fig. 6: Results using control strategies.

WITH control strategies			
Electricity consumption	Winter	Summer	Autumn
	109%	93%	94%
Electricity cost	Winter	Summer	Autumn
	107% *2022	92%	92%
	102% *2023		

4. CONCLUSIONS

For the conclusions, his study has evaluated the benefits of thermal storage for the residential sector, for the real case of the IWER building, using as TES the subway cistern it has. The results obtained reproduce the benefits that we wanted to study with orders of magnitude very similar to those found in the literature. First, regarding the use of the TES for peak shaving, a reduction of installed power of 18%-15% was obtained, which, at the same time, stabilizes the operation of the heat pumps by reducing their partial load hours, as well as their on and off times. Second, we applied tested control strategies based on two variables: excess PV production and electricity price. The results show that both strategies improve the energy efficiency of the building compared to not using them and reduce the consumption of grid energy in the case of photovoltaics as well as the cost of grid electricity. However, in times of low PV production, grid consumption can be even higher, due to an increase in production resulting from a higher thermal jump in the heat pumps. Whether this consumption is higher or lower is highly dependent on the electricity price for the year in question. For future studies, it is recommended to perform a parametric study simulating in full years, instead of typical weeks. This should be done for several years, including future estimates of both climate and electricity prices and an automated programming of control strategies instead of manual ones. These results would be communicated into the work package of the HVACR in the refurbishing project and considered.

5. BIBLIOGRAPHY

[1] E. Annunziata, M. Frey, and F. Rizzi, "Towards nearly zero-energy buildings: The state-of-art of national regulations in Europe," *Energy*, vol. 57, pp. 125–133, Aug. 2013, doi: 10.1016/J.ENERGY.2012.11.049.

[2] "In focus: Energy efficiency in buildings | Comisión Europea." https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/focus-energy-efficiency-buildings-2020-lut-17_es (accessed Nov. 26, 2022).

[3] "Residencial, comercial e institucional." <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cambio-climatico/temas/mitigacion-politicas-y-medidas/edificacion.aspx> (accessed Jun. 12, 2023).

[4] S. Tsemekidi Tzeiranaki, P. Bertoldi, M. Economidou, E. L. Clementi, and M. Gonzalez-Torres, "Determinants of energy consumption in the tertiary sector: Evidence at European level," *Energy Reports*, vol. 9, pp. 5125–5143, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.ENERGY.2023.03.122.

[5] A. Chadly, R. Rajeevkumar Urs, M. Wei, M. Maalouf, and A. Mayyas, "Techno-economic assessment of energy storage systems in green buildings while considering demand uncertainty," *Energy Build*, vol. 291, p. 113130, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2023.113130.

- [6]Y. Li, G. Rosengarten, C. Stanley, and A. Mojiri, "Electrification of residential heating, cooling and hot water: Load smoothing using onsite photovoltaics, heat pump and thermal batteries," *J Energy Storage*, vol. 56, p. 105873, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.EST.2022.105873.
- [7]A. Rinaldi, S. Yilmaz, M. K. Patel, and D. Parra, "What adds more flexibility? An energy system analysis of storage, demand-side response, heating electrification, and distribution reinforcement," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 167, p. 112696, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.RSER.2022.112696.
- [8]E. A. Ragoowansi, S. Garimella, and A. Goyal, "Realistic utilization of emerging thermal energy recovery and storage technologies for buildings," *Cell Rep Phys Sci*, vol. 4, no. 5, p. 101393, May 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.XCRP.2023.101393.
- [9]W. Lyu et al., "Influence of the water tank size and air source heat pump size on the energy saving potential of the energy storage heating system," *J Energy Storage*, vol. 55, p. 105542, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2022.105542.
- [10]Y. Li, N. Zhang, and Z. Ding, "Investigation on the energy performance of using air-source heat pump to charge PCM storage tank," *J Energy Storage*, vol. 28, p. 101270, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.EST.2020.101270.
- [11]A. Heinz and R. Rieberer, "Energetic and economic analysis of a PV-assisted air-to-water heat pump system for renovated residential buildings with high-temperature heat emission system," *Appl Energy*, vol. 293, p. 116953, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.APENERGY.2021.116953.
- [12]M. Dannemand, I. Sifnaios, Z. Tian, and S. Furbo, "Simulation and optimization of a hybrid unglazed solar photovoltaic-thermal collector and heat pump system with two storage tanks," *Energy Convers Manag*, vol. 206, p. 112429, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.ENCONMAN.2019.112429.
- [13]A. Sohani et al., "Techno-economic evaluation of a hybrid photovoltaic system with hot/cold water storage for poly-generation in a residential building," *Appl Energy*, vol. 331, p. 120391, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.APENERGY.2022.120391.
- [14]V. Palani, S. P. Vedavalli, V. P. Veeramani, and S. Sridharan, "Optimal operation of residential energy Hubs include Hybrid electric vehicle & Heat storage system by considering uncertainties of electricity price and renewable energy," *Energy*, vol. 261, p. 124952, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.ENERGY.2022.124952.
- [15]F. Agyenim and N. Hewitt, "The development of a finned phase change material (PCM) storage system to take advantage of off-peak electricity tariff for improvement in cost of heat pump operation," *Energy Build*, vol. 42, pp. 1552–1560, Sep. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2010.03.027.
- [16]N. Pardo Garcia, A. Montero, J. Martos, and J. Urchueguia, "Optimization of hybrid – ground coupled and air source – heat pump systems in combination with thermal storage," *Appl Therm Eng*, vol. 30, pp. 1073–1077, Jun. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2010.01.015.
- [17]E. Osterman and U. Stritih, "Review on compression heat pump systems with thermal energy storage for heating and cooling of buildings," *J Energy Storage*, vol. 39, p. 102569, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.EST.2021.102569.
- [18]M. J. Kim, B. M. Seo, J. M. Lee, J. M. Choi, and K. H. Lee, "Operational behavior characteristics and energy saving potential of vertical closed loop ground source heat pump system combined with storage tank in an office building," *Energy Build*, vol. 179, pp. 239–252, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2018.09.025.